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Research Article

Evaluation of Urban Productive Social Safety Net Project Implementation Practices; A mixed Method Empirical Evidences from Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-City Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

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Abstract: Urban poverty and social inequality remain critical challenges in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, where poverty rates have exceeded national averages. In response, the Government of Ethiopia launched the Urban Productive Safety Net Program (UPSNP) in 2016, adapting the rural safety net model. However, limited empirical evidence exists on its implementation in urban contexts.

This study aimed to evaluate UPSNP implementation practices in Nifas Silk Lafto Sub-city using a descriptive mixed-method approach. Quantitative data were collected from 250 respondents (87% response rate) and analyzed using SPSS, while qualitative insights were obtained from 12 key informant interviews and 8 focus group discussions. The analysis was guided by nine project management knowledge areas, with a high reliability score (Cronbach's alpha = 0.946).

Findings indicate good to excellent performance in integration, stakeholder management, cost, quality, human resources, risk, and procurement practices, reflecting strong institutional capacity. However, moderate performance was observed in schedule management, with inconsistencies across implementation sites. Qualitative results highlighted challenges such as bureaucratic procedures, market price fluctuations, and limited operational capacity.

The study concludes that UPSNP implementation in Nifas Silk Lafto Sub-city demonstrates strong project management foundations but requires improvements in time management, coordination, and feedback mechanisms to ensure long-term sustainability and impact. The findings contribute to urban social protection literature and provide practical insights for policymakers and development practitioners.

Keywords: *Urban Poverty, Social Inequality, Urban Productive Safety Net Program (UPSNP), Project Implementation, Mixed Methods, Addis Ababa, Social Protection, Ethiopia*

1. Introduction

Ethiopia, like many rapidly urbanized developing countries, it has experienced an accelerated rural to urban migration of the population due to various pooling and pushing factors. However the migration into urban areas caused serious socioeconomic problem. Initially, this mass population migrations into cities were without a commensurate expansion in employment opportunities, and social services. It has indicated that urban infrastructure is unaddressed paradox and this has created significant socioeconomic problems World Bank (2015). Secondly, the overgrowing unplanned urbanization and rapped urban population growth in Ethiopia has created social crises in most urban areas. These social crises included serious housing shortages and homelessness, lack of

basic infrastructures, growth of informal settlements and increments of destitute urban residents Habitat (2017).

The impacts of urban poverty was much more complex in newly grown and emerged cities than the older cities in Ethiopia. The newly emerged urban areas were affected by rapidly grown unplanned urbanization, and unbalanced population growth in a fragmented and underdevelopment of urban infrastructures. In addition the increased lack of employment opportunities, and lack of sufficient local urban infrastructural developments multiplied social crises conditions in newly emerged sub-urban and urban areas Teferi and Newman (2017). As part of a responses for poverty reduction and alleviation of the urban social crises the Ethiopian government has launched and familiarized the urban productive social

safety net program in 2016. The program was aimed to reduce the widespread urban social and economic inequalities, and to minimize the resultant effect of extreme urban poverty.

In fact Ethiopia has been implemented rural social safety net program in rural areas since 1970s to respond for widespread poverty, famine and starvation. It has brought significant progress and contributed a lot on local socioeconomic and livelihood development efforts. The rural safety net program, initially was focused on relief based humanitarian assistance's and later in 2002 it was reformed from rural food for the hungry to rural productive social safety net program. The reform was made by incorporated basic principles of predictability, sustainability and long term impacts. These reform have increased positive performances on rural productive social safety net program which was initiated, promoted, and leded Ethiopian government to cascade the program implementation in urban areas. The improvements in rural social safety net program have brought significant changes. It has contributions for sustainable local developments especially in urban infrastructural building, solid waste management and urban greening. Following the positive returns from rural productive social safety net program in Ethiopia the interventions were interred into urban areas aimed to alleviate urban poverty and inequality. The beginning of the implementation of urban safety net program was aimed to respond for urban poverty, vulnerabilities and to contribute for urban sustainable social development by reduce urban poverty, inequality and extreme vulnerabilities(WFP, 2018).

Urban productive social safety net program was the first large-scale, government-led programme supported by World Bank and Ethiopian government in collaboration. The programme initially has started to be implemented in the selected 11 poverty affected urban areas including Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa. Later it has expanded to 77 large and smaller cities urban poor in needs of safety net supports. The program principal aims was to reduce urban chronic poverty, to enhance livelihood opportunities, and to build resilience among urban households. It was targeted those households living below the absolute poverty line and aimed to enhance their consumption, improve employ-ability, support micro-enterprise development. It has helped to strengthen resilience from shocks and problems. The programme have been engaged beneficiaries in productive activities as if they were able to work and engage in labor-intensive public works. Furthermore, the elderly, chronically ill, disabled persons and other vulnerable groups were received unconditional direct transfers to cover their basic needs and to keep their well-being in conditions crises (WFP, 2018).

Addis Ababa city administration has the largest poor residents who were in needs of social safety net

supports. It has 28.1% of urban poverty rate which is the highest of the national average urban poverty rate 25.7% World Bank (2015). The selected study area that is Nifas Silk Lafto Sub-city is one of the largest sub-city administrated by Addis Ababa city Administration. It is the implementer of a project in the selected woredas. According to the population census of 2007 Nefas Silk Lafto Sub-city have the total population of 397,234. The annual population growth rate was 6.1. The sub-city has accommodated the total of 13 local administrations (Woredas). Of the total local administration 8 of the woredas were engaged on this program implementation practices. The rate of poverty in the sub-city was 6% which was among the highest as compared with other sub-cities PIM, (2016).

The sub-city has selected for investigation since it have better experiences in terms of implementation of urban social safety net program. It was one of the sub city that have poor scholarly coverage in-terms of evaluation of urban safety net project implementation practices. Furthermore, the sub-city lacks contextually supported empirical evidences on project management practices that shows the outcome of the interventions. The existed previous researches were predominantly focused on rural productive social safety net program. The few previous studies on urban social safety net project implementation in Addis Ababa and other urban areas were focused typically on impacts or outcome of the project for food security, livelihood improvements, and socioeconomic impacts. Some others were also focused on single items selected from nine project management knowledge areas. This has suggested that most previous studies were insufficiently applied the nine knowledge of project management areas to evaluate urban social safety net project. So, this significant lack and absences of sufficient scholastic contextualized study program on evaluation of comprehensive project management knowledge areas. These was because of urban safety net program was fairly new as it compared with rural safety net programme and lacks sufficient empirical studies.

As far as the knowledge of the researcher in Ethiopia particularly in Addis Ababa no one had conducted a comprehensive evaluative of investigation of urban productive social safety net program implementation practices. It has applied the holistic nine project management knowledge areas for the investigation of the study. Thus, this gap highlighted the need for this research study. This study were highly contributed to fill this gaps since it has addressed lack of locally contextualized empirical evidences on evaluation of the project progress. The study were caused by the absences of empirically supported actions, and decisions and it have poor project accomplishment performances. Thus, this study has conducted an on evaluation of urban productive social safety net project by applied the comprehensive nine project management knowledge areas. These are

were project integration, scope, schedule, costs quality, communication, procurement, human resources and risks management practices.

The study has contributed for different actors who were engaged in implementation of urban productive social safety net project. In the first instances it has offered empirical evidences for project managers, social workers, policymakers, development practitioners, urban social safety net program planners, and stakeholders. On the other side it have contributed as sources documents served for references. In more it has served as the the sources documents for the local project implementer as sources of empirical findings of the study. In addition the study have enormous implications for project performances output. It has served as reference document for major social protection programming delivery. Finally, it can contributed to the body of literature on urban poverty reduction, social protection efforts, and provided context-specific insights relevant to Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

2. Research Design, Tools And Methodology

The study has intended to evaluate the implementation of urban social safety net project in Nifas Silik lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. It has descriptive research design and has applied a mixed research method to conduct an investigation. The usage of mixed research method was aimed to get breadth and depths of understanding on the ongoing implementation of the project Creswell, (2003). It has aimed to describe the evaluation of results by statistical mean and standard deviations. In regards to study population and area the study area have the total of 13 local administrations(Woredas) 8 local administrations (Woredas) in Nefas Silk Lafto Sub-city. The study total population was finite which was 1,032. The total population composition included program management and employees at various labels. The used data collection tools were sample survey questionnaires. It has open-ended questionnaires for focus group discussion and key informant interviews to generate the qualitative insights.

The purposive sampling technique were used to screen the local administration so called woredas. The sampled woredas were selected because of their vast experience in project implementation and management practices. They were initially selected districts to implement the projects. They have screened clients who have better experience on project implementation practices. In addition, availability of experienced and knowledgeable personnel to respond for questions were taken into considered to screen samples.

The sample size were calculated by using Yemane Formula. Yemane formula has used to determine the

sample size and it is appropriate for finite populations. since the stud the population finite population numbers the formula has selected as appropriate.

Formula

$$n = N / (1 + N(e^2))$$

Where: n = sample size N = total population e = margin of error (level of precision)

Sample Used in the Study

Given: N = 1,032 and e = 0.05

$$n = 1032 / (1 + 1032 * 0.05^2)$$

$$n = 1032 / (1 + 1032 * 0.0025)$$

$$n = 1032 / 3.58 \quad n = \underline{288}$$

A sample size was determined and 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error where considered , the sample size of was 288 taken for the investigations.

The qualitative data were aimed to used to generate depths of insights and perspective on evaluation of urban productive social safety net program. They key informants were initially recruited taken their sufficient experiences and knowledge in implementation of urban social safety net program in their respective districts. In addition, the quantitative data was analyzed by applied statistical software version 22. The software has used to calculate the mean and standard deviation scores. The qualitative data were gathered by employed thematic analysis approach which was used to carryout the study analysis. At the end the integration of both data was made at the stage of interpretation to get depths and breadth of answers for the research questions and for final discussions.

Since the principal aim of the study was to evaluate urban social safety net project management practices the depth and breadth data sources were required. It has also used both the quantitative and qualitative approaches to generate the comprehensive understandings about the study. The qualitative data were includes 8 focus group discussions, and 12 key informants responses. The data were gathered by the the evaluative questions were prepared from all the nine project management knowledge areas. In the other ways the quantitative data were included sample survey of 288 samples and of distributed 288 questionnaires 250 successfully responded and returned. It has 87% of response rate. So, the study result and discussion included the overall response rate, demographic information. The final results of the study has presented by the three major themes and nine sub-themes. The validity of instruments was maintained by standard questionnaires and based on previous knowledge on the litterateurs reviewed. The validity and reliability test were undertaken and the reliability of the collected data was tested by applied Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of the the research objective.

Table 1. Summary of Reliability Tests of Cronbach's Alpha

Objectives	N	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
How it looks like the urban productive social safety net project management practices in Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city.	250	.946	26

Source: Own Survey Result, 2022

As the above table clearly depicted that the reliability and validity value of the research objective as per Cronbach Alpha is .946 coefficient from 26 indicators. According to Cronbach's Alpha coefficient if it is equal or above .70 it is satisfactory to say it reliable and valid (polit, Back& Hungler, 2001). So, the study objective have got 0.946 Cronbach Alpha value. This asserts that the validity and reliability was scored more than satisfactory and it has exceeded to the acceptable thresholds 0.70.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher has adhered to ethical principles. Initially, respondents and other contributors have introduced about purpose of the study and all participation were based on voluntary engagements. The responsible beneficiaries, project managers, officers and key informants have entered on informed consents. In addition the ethical principles, and efforts have made to keep confidentiality and anonymity through the application of pseudo names and other measures. Furthermore research ethics been adhered on ethical principles started from the proposal development, data collection, analyses, presentation and publication process. In all sense the study has assured and keeps ethical standards throughout the process of the investigation.

3. Results and Discussion

The results has presented the evaluation of urban productive social safety net project implementation practices in Nifas Silik lafto sub-city. It has included the sample survey of 250 respondents as quantitative output and 8 focus group discussions and 12 key informant results. The study results and discussion have presented by using three major thematic presentations. The three major themes applied on analysis are discussed hereunder. The first theme has discussed the evaluation of project governance and planning which includes sub themes such as project integration, scope, schedule and costs management. The second theme was evaluation of project implementation and performances which includes project quality, procurement, and human resources management practices. The third major theme was evaluation of monitoring and risks management practices which includes risks and stakeholders management practices.

In each theme have both qualitative and quantitative outputs that are presented and analyzed concurrently and discussed by integration of the two data outputs at the end. The quantitative outputs has presented by applied the standard deviation (SD) and mean. The mean statistical values implied average mean values or central average data sets. It is largely shown the average level of study variables found among study participants. The standard deviation value shows the level of variability and consistency within responses respectively. It has used to assess consistency and variability among study variables. It helps to measure and compare indicators by applied single summary of values in each themes and shown varieties and spread close to the mean or the variability or consistencies among respondents responses.

The standard application of mean and standard deviation in this study has adopted from a statistical standard applied by a researcher Henchoz, Meylan, & Santos-Eggimann (2016). The standard has helped for the standardization or categorization of scale of measurements in the study. It helps to interpret the number into meaningful outputs. These standards sated that "if the mean value is <2.49 = low (very poor), second if mean value $>2.5 < 3.49$ = moderate, third mean value $> 3.5 < 4.49$ = good, fourth mean $> 4.5 < 4.75$ = very good, and if fifth mean value is in between $4.74-5$ = excellent.

The value of standard deviation shows how the spread, or consistent across response in the study. The standard deviation value has presented by the standards that have states that "if the standard deviation value is less than 1 the response were consistent among the study variables" which implies that the respondents have relatively similar stands to respond for the questions. Second, "if the standard deviation is in between SD 1-1.5 the responses were moderately variable or less consistent among study variables. It implies that the respondents were slightly vary. Whereas, if standard deviation is greater than 1.5 the response have higher variability which means it was less consistent. This implied that response of the respondents were differ widely among study variables. There were no significant consistencies among response of respondents. In addition the qualitative outputs has interpretation that were through thematic categorization approach.

3.1. Evaluation of Project Governance and Planning

In this theme the urban productive social safety net project implementation practices results has discussed focused on

the project integration, and scope management practices. The total of 250 successfully responded survey participants result and discussions were presented based on standard mean and standard deviation values. In this theme the results of an evaluation of project scope and integration management were presented below.

3.1.1. Evaluation of Project Integration Management

In this theme the project integration management were undertaken to evaluate the project services packages, coordination's among services components, integration, planning and tracking of progress.

Table:1 Survey Results on Evaluation of Project Integration management Practices

	Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
1	Project services packages were strongly integrated to achieve desired sated goal.	4.5200	Very good	1.12010	Moderate variability of responses.
2	The lack of coordination on project components, resulted inefficient progresses.	3.1200	Moderate	1.20840	>>
3	The planning, and tracking are well integrated, so that decisions made at different departments have been consistently practiced.	4.5640	Very good	0.96095	Consistent or relatively similar stands.
	Sub-theme Average	4.068	Good	1.09	Slight variability

Source: Own Filed Survey April to June, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city

As the table above clearly illustrated that the first and third indicators have strong performances with a mean value of 4.5200 and 4.5640, this result has falls on “very good”level (Henchoz, Meylan, & Santos-Eggimann 2016). It has suggested that project integration management have both integration of project services packages and progress tracking practices through planned operations. However, the corresponding standard deviation values were for both 1st and 2nd indicators were 1.12010 and 0.96095 respectively. It has implied project services package integration management practices as it were varied among project implementer sites. This has indicated that the project have the consistent ingratiation in planing, and in tracking progress. In addition this standard deviation scores has reflected the decisions made that were consistently implemented across all woredas (lower implementation sites).

The second indicator mean value is (M= 3.120), which falls on “ moderate” category with slightly varied responses across the indicator of the respondents. This has implied the lower impacts on a project performances due to challenges related to lack of coordination on project components. It has suggested that the poor project coordination among project sub-systems or components were slightly indicated uneven project integration practices across project implementation sites. Finally, overall average mean value of this theme was 4.068 which fall on “good”

category. This has suggested that the overall good project schedule management practices and the overall standard deviation value was 1.09 which implied slight consistency among respondents responses. This has shown an average slight variability on project integration management practices across project implementation sites.

The qualitative insights confirmed the survey finding. The focus group discussion participants were agreed that the project integration among its services packages, in operational planning and tracking of progress. They also disclosed that the project integration management were not uniformly implemented across all project implementer woredas (site). In similar tone the key informants assured project planning framework were existed but their enforcement varied. It has largely resulted inconsistency on integration of the project services packages. On this regard the previous empirical study finding by Teferi & Newman (2017), and World Bank (2018), have founded that in the project implementation practices significant level of project integration was pivotal to enhance urban social safety net programme implementation effectiveness. But, still solving woreda (project implementation sites) bottlenecks was a significant concern that have minimized the issues, and needs careful attentions.

3.1.2. Evaluation of Project Schedule Management

In this sub-theme the project schedule management practices were evaluated in relation to adherence to project timelines, project activities monitoring practices

against with operational time frame, and in cases of incidences of poor schedule management practices.

Table 5: Project Evaluation of Schedule Management Practices where N=250

S/N	Indictors	M	Interpretatio n	SD	Interpretation
1	The project operations were adhered to project timeline.	3.3800	Good	1.12010	Less consistent or moderately vary
2	Th project activities implementation practices were effectively monitored by the project team.	3.1600	Moderate	1.20840	Less consistent or moderately vary
3	The poor schedule managements, and prevailing delay affected project accomplishment progress.	2.1640	Low or very poor	0.9890	Consistent is high
	Average	2.90013	Moderate	1.1058	Less consistent moderately vary

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

The table above clearly depicted that the initial item mean value (M, 3.38) fall under “good” level of evaluation that means the project operations and with less consistent responses. It has implied that the project operation were adhered to operational periods on public works, livelihood interventions and direct cash transfers implementation practices. The corresponding standard deviation scores was (SD=1.12.). It have shown slighter variability on responses. This has implied that certain inconsistencies were found across project implementation sites in aspects of adherence to schedules. The second item mean value was (M=3.16) and it has placed on “moderate” level of evaluation. The standard deviation scores (SD= 1.20840) among the respondents. This has implied slight variability among respondent responses. This has indicated the existences of effective schedule monitoring by project teams at district levels. But, still there is inconsistency across project implementation sites. Meaning while some of the project site were completed all deliverable and activities on time by applied effective schedule management whereas some others were not done as per the expected rate and time given.

The third indicator respondents have mean score (M=2.164) which falls on “moderately” disagreed response. This has implied that poor schedule management and over-delay significantly affected the overall project accomplishment progress. The standard deviation score of this item is (SD=0.9890), which indicated the highest consistency among respondent responses. This has implied a very low or very poor impacts on poor schedule management which have a possible impacts on project accomplishment progress.

This has implied that in the study area though delays were sometimes happened, it was not perceived as severely reduced overall project accomplishment progress. The average mean value is (M=2.90013), which have fall on “moderate” category which has evaluated the project schedule management practices as it was moderately performed which was not good and excellent. This has shown existences of time management problems but, it is less consistent and not uniformly happened across project sites.

The qualitative insights on this regard has indicated that project operational period management is generally kept at strong performances. The focus group discussion participants argued that all other project services packages such as cash transfer generally followed planned timelines but, relatively schedules were not properly managed public work activities and livelihood support schemes. They have reported external factors such as inflation, over bureaucratic administration and scarcity of resources were taken as major constraints in managing schedule of public work and livelihood support engagements. They also acknowledge that project schedule management delays were inconsistently occurred across project implementation sites and it was at the conditions of manageable level. In addition the key informants have acknowledged that the project operation have its own calender that goes with the government fiscal operational year but, the delays were rarely occurred due to donor grant disbursement and allocation gaps, incomplete project operational staffs, and woreda level administrative problems. The key informants in this regards acknowledged that the project operational period were monitored centrally by project monitoring and evaluation

framework but, still its enforcement were not uniform, resulted less consistent performance across project implementation sites.

In general the finding of the study on project schedule management ranges from moderate to good levels and have found that project operations were adhered to timelines to the level of good evaluation result but not very good and excellent. The overall finding of the project schedule management was moderately evaluated which implied inconsistencies in adherence to schedules across project implementation sites. This finding is strongly consistent with the study finding of

the previous public project research conducted by Ayalew & Tadesse, (2018) in Ethiopia. They have found that the possible causes of delays in public projects were bureaucratic procedures, payment processing delays, and poor coordination.

3.1.3. Evaluation of Project Cost Management Practices

In this sub-theme an evaluation of the project costs management practices were presented in context of its planned financial operations, costs control mechanisms, budget management and status of occasional derivations form the planned operational budgets.

Table:5 Evaluation of Project Costs Management Practices N=250

S/n	Items	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
1	The grant budget were well-planned and financial resources were allocated and disbursed properly.	4.6880	Very good	1.12754	Modeartly variable
2	Project did not have adequate costs control, hence inefficiently, and improper budget management was not practiced.	3.1200	Modearte	1.13080	Modeartly variable
3	The occasional deviations from the approved budget has affected timely implementation of project activities.	3.1560	Modearte	1.17473	Modeartly variable
	Average	3.6547	Good	1.144357	Modeartly variable

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

As the table above clearly depicted that the first mean value is M, 4.6880 which falls under “very good category.” It have demonstrated very strong agreement on grant budget management that were carefully planned, and with the financial resources which were fairly allocated and disbursed across project components. However, this results have the standard deviation value 1.12754 which implied less consistent responses across project implementer sites. This has implied that the project budget planing and financial resources as it were not consistent across project management practices. In addition it has suggested uneven practices on planned operations across project implementer woredas. The second item mean value was M = 3.120, which

fall under “moderate” category. This has demonstrated that respondents were acknowledge the occurrences of costs control weakness but as it was rarely affected the financial operations. In addition it has shown that such constraints of weak costs control may be situational rather than systematic.

The third item have mean value M, 3.156, which falls under “moderate” category. The respondents were evaluated concern related to episodic deviation from

approved budget as it has occurrences to the minimal status and has less impacts on timely implementation practices. In general this result has largely demonstrated a minimal occasional deviations from the approved budget and it may not affected the periodic implementation of the project activities. Lastly, the overall mean value was 3.6547 which fall on “good” category. It has suggested that costs management performances in the urban productive social safety net project were practiced as “good” in aspects of budget planing, resources allocations, and expenditure controls. The average standard deviation score is also 1.144357 which falls on “moderate” category. This has demonstrated less consistent practices of project costs management practices in the study area.

The focus group discussion participants noted that the project as the project was financed jointly by Ethiopian government and world Bank. Its financial management goes though the government finance and administration systems which have a strict applications of expenditures and income controls. Thus, the allocated budgeted were proportionally allocated allocated and disbursements were made for all project implementer woredas. It the allocation and disbursement have done by the government structure from city administration to sub-city and woreda and

ketena level administrations. They have reported that clients have the predictable financial earnings from the project services, accompanied with transparent financial managements that have strengthen trusts to all project stakeholders. In addition they have noted that the payment timing for in services, for graduation and amount of payments for each supports were fixed. This has reduced conflicts of interests among services providers and services users as long as the services and expectations were clearly sated and clients were acted accordingly. The participant added more that they have notated that project direct supports and graduation payments were fixed. This has made them highly vulnerable and exposed for market price change, which reduced money values by significantly minimized the its purchasing power.

Furthermore key informants corroborated that costs planning and financial controls were followed strict operational financial management standards for both the government and the donor (World Bank). In the project money disbursement were calculated by its investment return rate and by its productivity yields for those who have been engaged on productive activities engaged in various paying public works. On this regards the key informants disclosed that minor project budget deviations were existed but still it have

managed by financial management steps. It has often disrupted overall project implementation at operational woredas but not common to all woredas.

In general the surevy finding regarding on the project costs management have fall from good to very good costs management practices especially in budget planing, resources allocation and disbursements. These particular finding was highly consistent with World Bank (2018) assessment, that have reported and documented that urban productive social safety net program financial management systems as relatively strong. The qualitative insight acknowledged as it have it have duel close donors technical supports and application of advanced standardized financial management systems. While project has very good performances in costs management practices which is higher than previous research findings. The research by Hoddinott et al.,(2012), on rural safety net project has reported moderate deviations from approved budgets that were required budget reallocation and adjustments services.

3.1.4. Evaluation of Project Scope Management Practices

In this sub-theme the study finding has assessed project scope management changes without due authorization, ambiguity and confusion in project scopes, and criteria prior communications .

Table 6: Surevy Résultats on Project Scope Management Practices

S/N	Indictors	Indicator	Mean	Interpretation	SD
1	The scope were strictly followed, and changes were not made without due authorization.	4.5240	Very good	0.86488	High consistency of responses.
2	The ambiguities in defining project scope, causes confusion for staff and beneficiaries.	3.1120	Modearte	1.02688	Moderately consistent,
3	The scope is unclear, and inadequately managed, and have misaligned activities.	3.1200	Modearte	1.13080	moderately vary
4	The criteria for beneficiaries selections are clearly stated and shared to all the relevant stakeholders.	4.6520	Very good	1.00752	Moderately vary or slightly vary
	Sub-theme Average	3.852	Good	1.00752	Average moderate varibiliets

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

As the table above clearly presented that the first indicator which has evaluated the extents of strict follow-ups of planned activities that should not go beyond from the original scope without authorization. This item has scaled as mean scores of 4.5240 which falls under “very good” category. The corresponding standard value was 0.86488 which indicated the highly consistent responses. This has indicated that deviations from the sated scope were formally

managed to extent of very good practices. In addition, informal scope creep were significantly prevented. The second indicator result have the mean value of 3.112 falls under “ moderate” category and its corresponding standard deviation scores were 1.02688 which implied the less consistent responses across the project implementer woredas. This has indicated that respondents were moderately agreed on the incidences of ambiguities or inconsistencies in defining project scopes. This has causes

confusion for staff and beneficiaries. It has implied that ambiguities and inconsistencies in defining project scope were found moderate. But, it was less likely to causes confusions on staffs and beneficiaries.

Third indicator result mean value was 3.1200 which falls under “moderate” category with the corresponding stand deviation scores 1.1308, which implied less consistent responses across respondent responses. This has indicated that unclear and inadequately managed project scope is less consistently found across project implementer districts (woredas). In addition the results has demonstrated that the respondents to some extent were agreed on the existences of unclear and inadequate project scope management practices but, it was not common for all implementer sites. The fourth indicator evaluation result was “very good” and it has indicated that eligibility rules and scope boundaries are clearly articulated and communicated to relevant stakeholders with slightly vary responses across project implementation sites. Finally, the average survey result has indicated that project scope management in implementing urban productive safety net project were good. However, it needs the targeted intervention to minimize inconsistency in scope interpretation and in careful delivery of services and helped to brought high uniformity and consistencies.

The qualitative data that were collected from focus group discussion participant revealed that eligibility criteria for inclusion or exclusion of clients were clearly defined and shared for all project implementer in the project sites. They have noted that their project implementation sites were implemented by using formally approved and authorized operational standard protocols that have clearly defined scope management directions. This has reduced unauthorized changes and

avoided confusions on its operations at the grass root level. Furthermore, the key informants also addressed that inconsistencies were rarely occurred at the lower level operations. It have minor and manageable impacts over the overall project performances and scope creep were prevented in their project implementation sites. As to the key informant since project inception programme operational standards, policies and protocols were familiarized for all implementer woredas and to all project management teams and confusions on scope management were reduced at all level.

In general the finding of the study have found that project scope management were generally good and it has very strong compliance with planned activities. The beneficiary inclusion and exclusion criteria were clearly defined. In addition the study findings have found moderate ambiguity in some project implementation sites which was highly consistent with World Bank (2020) evaluation of urban productive social safety net project implementation in Ghana and Uganda and it have found that contextualized definitions have created inconsistency among project implementer sites.

3.2. Evaluation of Project Implementation and Performance Management Practices

In this theme the project implementation and performances management practices were presented an evaluation of project quality, human resources and procurement practices and each have discussed hereunder.

3.2.1. Project Quality Management Practices

In this sub-theme the project quality management practices has evaluated in terms of quality on project deliverable, routine monitoring, supervision and technical supports, and occasional laps in quality control mechanisms .

Table: 7 Summary of Survey Result of Project Quality Management Practices

Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
Project deliverable such as public works, direct cash transfers, and livelihood supports were at expected quality standards and specifications.	4.5260	Very good	1.16570	Less consistent/ Moderately variable
The routine monitoring, supervision and technical supports were undertaken to look quality of outputs.	4.6120	Very good	1.02688	Modertlyvariable
The occasional lapses in quality control leading to outputs without the intended quality standards.	3.4560	Modearte	0.96112	Consistent similar stand
In your project sit, the absences of effective quality management practices leads to the generation of poor-quality deliverable.	3.7800	Good	0.95459	>>
Average	4.0935	Good	1.02707	Slightly vary/ moderately vary

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

The above table above illustrated that the first indicator have mean score 4.5260 which fall under the category of “Very Good.” It have showing higher level of adherence that project activities, outputs and services packages such as direct cash transfers, livelihood supports and public work schemes have fulfilled the required quality standard and specifications. The corresponding standard deviation was 1.16570 which indicated less consistent responses across project implementer woredas. The More similar result have found the second indicator have the highest mean score $M= 4.61$ which falls under “ very good” category of mean value. It implied that routine monitoring, supervision and technical supports were significantly ensured quality of the project outcome. The result shows that regular supervision and technical backstopping are formally and systemically integrated within the project implementation practices. The corresponding standard deviation scores were 1.02688 were less consistent responses across project implementer sites.

The third indicator has the mean value of 3.4560 which falls under “ moderate” category. This has implied occasional lapses in quality control the affects project quality management practices and it has rarely happened. The corresponding standard deviation scores were 0.96112 which indicated consistent response across project implementer sites. This implied that occasional laps in quality control were consistently affected the project performances. The fourth indicator also has scored the mean value of 3.7800 which falls on “ good” category and the corresponding standard deviation scores were 0.95459 which indicated consistent responses across project implementer sites. This implied that some respondents acknowledge periodic project quality challenges that hinder full adherence with standard and this result is relatively less consistent across project sites.

The overall mean value was 4.00935 which falls under “ good” category with overall standard deviation of 1.02707 that has fall under the “ overall good” level of project quality management practices. It has indicated that project quality planing, assurances and control mechanisms were generally effective in ensuring that project outcomes have meet sated standards. In general the activities has indicted that the project management quality was widely accepted practices but still the

intensity and consistency may vary across implementation sites. The qualitative insights on the project quality management practices have indicted that project services packages have predefined quality standards and interventions were familiarized and routinely monitored by various level project quality managers.

The focus group discussion participants agreed there are factors that have reduced quality of the project services such as delays on procurement, lower standardization, market inflation and incompatibility of support amounts. The participants acknowledged that the factors that have been occurred in the project implementation practices were managed through the application of regular supervision and technical supports. Similarly, the key informants have noted that the urban provocative safety net project implementation have its own quality management approach which is integral for project operations. They accepted that factors that have affected the quality of the project implementation were less consistently occurred at various levels mostly on front line sites but, these were managed by technical expertise and by continues technical backstopping practices.

The survey study finding has rated the project quality management as it is “good” but not very good and excellent practices. This implied that though project quality management supported by strong monitoring, supervision and technical backstopping but, still it did not reach on its highest potential. This finding was consistent with World Food Program (2018) public report that have publicized that project quality have maintained its quality through regular supervision that can increases quality of public works and livelihood outputs. In addition the study also have found that the existences of occasional quality laps across project sites in the study area. This finding also confirmed and consistent with the study finding conducted global equality and job quality trained which found that workload pressures and contextual constraints that have affected project output qualities (ILO, 2019).

3.2.2. Evaluation of Project Human resources management

In this theme the findings from the project human resources management practices were evaluated by its adequacy of personals employed, capacity building training provided and challenges of human resources management and its impacts on project performances.

Table: 8 Evaluation of Project Human Resources Management Practices

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	S. Déviation	Interpretation
The project have adequate and qualified personnel.	4.5780	Very good	1.35609	Modertly variable

The staffs were regularly trained and capacity to do their job efficiently strengthened.	4.5120	Very good	1.19514	Moderatly variable or less consistence
The excessive workload, staff turnover, or unclear role assignments affected performances.	2.1640	Low or very poor	0.94736	Consistent or on similar stands
The human resource management practices were weak and diminished project deliverable outputs.	3.1040	Moderate	1.32598	Moderatly variable or less consistence
Average	3.5895	Good	1.2061425	Moderatly variable or less consistences

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

As the table above clearly illustrated initial indicator mean value $M=4.5780$ which has falls within “very good category.” This has implied that the project implementation practices were have adequate and well qualified human resources employee. They were work in implementation of urban productive social safety net project activities and responses were less consistent across implementation sites. The second item has mean value 4.5120 similarly it has fall under “very good” category. This conclusive result shows that the regular staffs training and capacity building practices in urban productive social safety net project in the study area has implemented to the status of very good. however the standard deviation value 1.19514 which falls under “moderate” variability has indicted the less consistent responses and the difference on training and capacity building opportunities across project implementation sites. In contrary, the third item has mean value 2.1640 fall on “low” (very poor) category. This standard deviation scores was 0.94736 and it has the relatively low or less than 1 which implied a consistency of responses across project implementer sites. The mean score suggested that the respondents disagreed to the statement that states that workload pressure, staffs turnover or unclear role assignments significantly affected staffs performances. Despite this the fourth item mean value falls under moderate category that implied moderate variability among the respondents and it has suggested that weak human resources management practices moderately affected the project effectiveness but, it is less consist across project implementation sites.

The average mean value 3.5895 which falls under “good” category. Its gross corresponding average standard deviation values was 1.2061425 which reflected “moderate” variability in overall project implementation sites. It has implied that the respondents were largely shared positive perception on the effectiveness of human resources management practices with moderate variation across project implementation sites. Overviews the result have indicted that human resources management on urban

productive social safety net project has indicted very strong staffing, capacity building bases, strong coordination and role clarity but there are still challenges at the project implementation districts which fall on works-forces effectiveness and fall of project performances.

The focus group discussion participants uniformly reported that project operational staffs were adequately and sufficiently trained and deployed though it have higher turnover rates. They have indicated that sustained capacity building scheme were increased staff efficiency and productivity at work. In addition, they have noted that higher staffs turn overs, increased workloads pressures and insufficient training opportunities were constraints for the project human resources management practices. But, still it dose no affect the project performances. In addition the key informant have noted that formal structured recruitment, training, employment and performances evaluation have brought significant contribution for fulfilling the required project work forces.

They have reported that staffs in the project operational areas have lower experiences and this call sustained training and capacity building to fill gaps. In the first sub-theme the study finding have reviled that the project have very strong human resources capacity and sufficient staffs were employed to carryout the project activities with sufficient capacity building training given to theme. The World Bank study (2015), have founded that Ethiopian investment in capacity building have strengthened staffs skills and knowledge and improves project implementation capacities. The other study conducted by Devereux et al., (2015) has found that staff turnover and unclear role assignments were challenges identified in the social protection project.

3.2.3. Procurement and Resource Management Practices

In this theme the evaluation of urban productive social safety net project implementation practices. The findings on project procurement and resources management practices in aspects of planned procurement of goods and services. The effective and efficient utilization of project

equipment and resources were undertaken and impacts of inefficiency in the project procurement and weak procurement has assessed and presented

Table 9: Evaluation of project procurement and resources management practices

Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
The procurement of goods, services and inputs-es were planned, and conducted in the timely and transparent manners.	4.7800	Excellent	0.92010	Consistent responses
The project resources such as equipment's and materials, were sufficiently available and effectively utilized.	3.2600	Modearte	1.20840	Moderately ,slightly consistent
The inefficiencies in the courses of procurement frequently affected the timely implementation of the project.	3.5080	Good	1.08381	Moderately slightly consistent
The weak procurement practise have brought shortages, delays, and minimized outputs.	3.268	Modearte	1.129817	Moderately slightly consistent
Average	3.704	Good	1.0855317	Moderately slightly consistent

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

As the table above clearly shows that the initial indicator mean value was 4.7800 falls on “excellent” category. This indicated significant higher achievements shown that the services and goods were performed at the given time. This has implied that respondents consistently expressed surpassing strong agreement that procurement of goods, services. This implied that the inputs was well planned and conducted in a timely and transparent manner. Its corresponding standard deviation scores was 0.92010 and it has shown the consistent responses across respondents. The second indicator has mean score 3.2600 which indicated which fall on “moderate” category. The mean value indicted that it has sufficient and effective usage of primary project resources such as equipment, materials, and service providers. It has implied that even if the procurement practices were strong there is less consistent resources usage at various project implementation sites. The third indicator mean value 3.5080 which falls on “moderate” category. This has implied that in the study area project procurement and resources allocation efficiencies have timely project implementation practices. The indicator standard deviation scores 1.08381 which indicated the less consistent responses across. This has suggested that the project procurement and resources allocation efficiency were consistent across project implementation sites.

The last indicator mean value was 3.704 that has falls on “good” category. This suggested that weak

procurement and resources management practices have leads to shortages, delays and minimal outputs and its standard deviation falls on 1.129817 which implied the consistent responses across woredas Finally, the average mean value was 3.704 which falls under “good” category. This has implied that the study area have an overall good level of procurement and resources management performances though it can progress towards higher level to very good and excellent procurement practices. The qualitative data output indicted that the project procurement process were strongly transparent and performed based on time. Despite of these utilization of the project good and services were not uniform across project implementation districts and sometime it have affected the overall project performances practices.

The key informants of the study also have found that procurement were followed established procedures, resources allocations and it has supported by close monitoring and evaluation of procurement performances across project implementation bi-annul and fiscal years performance. Lastly, the study finding on the project procurement practices achieved an excellent rate for costs management transparency and timelines. This have strongly confirmed with World Bank (2018) assessment finding that have reviled that urban productive social safety net project implementation procurement practices meet international fiduciary standards. The overall standard deviation score falls on moderate category and this has highly confirmed by the previous study finding which has stressed that procurement efficiencies dose not

usually changed into optimal resource deployment at operational levels (OECD, 2019).

3.3. Evaluation of the Project Enabling Environment Practices

In this theme the findings of the study both on evaluation of project risk managements, project stakeholders engagement and communication managements have presented

3.3.1. Project Risk Management

In this sub-theme the findings has an the evaluation of project risks management in relation with external and internal factors. The actions of monitoring of risky situations, and insufficient project implementation and weak risks management practices were assessed and presented.

Table 10: Summary of an Evaluation Results on Project Risks Management practices

Indictors	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
The possible risk on payment delays, resources shortage, external socioeconomic shocks and instability assessed.	4.5400	Very good	1.25086	Less consistant
There is frequent monitoring of identified risks, and appropriate risks mitigation actions were taken to reduce its impacts.	4.5680	Very good	1.08381	Less consistant
The project risks were not sufficiently managed and resulted disruptions in project implementation practices.	3.374	Moderate	1.167335	Less consistant
Project risks management practices were weak and exposed for unforeseen challenges.	3.268	Low/ very poor	1.129817	Less consistant
Average	3.9375	Good	1.1579555	Less consistant

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

At the indicator level, the initial indicator mean value was 4.5400 which falls on “vary good” category. The result has indicated that the responses were strongly agreed that potential risks such as payment delays, resource shortages, and external socioeconomic shocks were systematically identified and assessed. The corresponding standard deviation was 1.25086 which implied less consistent responses across project implementer sites. While, standard deviation score indicated moderate dispersion, the high mean reflects widespread recognition of formal risk assessment practices. The second indicator have similar mean value of 4.5680 which falls under “very good” category. It has implied that frequent monitoring of identified risks and the implementation of appropriate risk mitigation measures taken in into practices in the study area.

The third indicator mean value was 3.374 which falls under “moderate” category. The corresponding standard deviation score was 1.167335 which shows less consistent responses across project implements. This suggested that it is less likely occurrence of poor project risk management and it has rarely affected the project implementation practices. Similarly, the mean value for the third mean values was 3.268 which falls

under very poor (low)” scores and its corresponding standard deviation values were 1.129817 which implied the less consistent responses across the project implementer wordas or sites. It has indicated that while risk management was generally effective, respondents acknowledged episodic weaknesses or contextual constraints. Finally, the aggregate mean value was 3.9375 which falls under “average good” category. It has indicated that risk identification, monitoring, and mitigation mechanisms were generally embedded within project operations. Its standard deviation was 1.157955 which implied the average less consistent response across project implementer sites. The overall standard deviation scored moderate variability, suggesting that although respondents largely perceived risk management practices positively, their application and effectiveness varied across project implementation sites.

The qualitative perspective from the focus group discussion participants and key informants were presented below. The focus group discussion participants agreed that in the project implementation practices anticipated risks such as payment delays, resources shortages and external market prices inflation s, social and economic instabilities were managed proactively without affecting the project accomplishment progress. They have reported that timely

risks mitigation measures taken have brought significant impacts and reduced disruptions during project implementation practices. In contrary the key informant has disclosed that risks management practices were not proactive in some project implementer woredas. They have noted that institutional learning on risks management played a significant role to proactively manage risks in project implementation.

3.3.2. Evaluation of Project Stakeholders Engagement and Communication

In this section the project stakeholders engagement and communication management evaluation results and discussions have presented in relation with participation of core stakeholders, effective communication of project deliverable and incidences of irregular communication gaps and lack of communication and stakeholders coordination.

Table 11: Project Stakeholders Engagement and Communication

Indictors	M	Interpretation	SD	Interpretation
The core stakeholders proactively participated in project planing, implementation and evaluation.	4.5560	Very good	1.01161	Less consistent Moderately vary
The stakeholders were effectively communicated about the project objectives, schedules, and clients duties.	4.9640	Excellenet	1.14891	Less consistent Moderately vary
The irregular gaps in communication and stakeholders participation resulted misunderstanding and delays in project performances.	3.6320	Good	1.03773	Modeartely variable, less consistance
Lack of communication and stakeholders participation that have brought limited engagements, weak feedback mechanisms.	2.4960	Low/very poor	0.88766	Highly consistent
Average	3.912	Good	1.021477 5	moderately vary

Source: Own Filed Survey, 2022 Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

As the table above clearly depicted that the first item has mean value of 4.56 which fall on “very good” category and the corresponding standard deviation scores 1.01161 which implied less consistent responses. The results has indicted that core stakeholders were proactively participated in project planing, implementation but its was not uniformly applied for all sites. More strongly the second indicator mean value was 4.9640 which fall on “excellent” category. The corresponding standard deviation score was 1.03773 which indicated moderate consistency among responses The result of this indicator has indicted that urban productive safety net project implementation in the study area have designed communication strategies effectively and implemented it successfully. But, still the practices were less uniformly applied across project implementation sites. In the third item mean value was 3.6320 which falls on “good” category and it corresponding standard deviation results was 1.03773 which shows less consistent responses. This has shown that significant number of respondents were acknowledged the existences of occasional communication gaps and irregular stakeholders

participation were leads to misunderstanding and implementation delays.

On contrary, the fourth indicator the mean value was 2.4960 which falls under low or very poor category and the results of corresponding standard deviations was 0.88766 implied the higher consistency among respondent responses. The respondents assured that lack of communication and poor stakeholders engagement were rarely or poorly reduced project accomplishment effectiveness. In conclusion the aggregate mean score of $M = 3.91$ falls within the “good” category. It has inform that stakeholder participation and communication systems were largely effective in encourage project planning, implementation, and evaluation. The overall standard deviation of $SD = 1.02$ reflects moderate variability, connote that while respondents generally shared positive perceptions, the depth and consistency of engagement and communication multifaceted across implementation sites.

The qualitative insights from focus group participants stressed that stakeholder were actively engaged in project workshops in planing, performance evaluation and technical follow up sessions. They have noted that clients

were well informed about project deliverable, resources and timeline but, still occasional communication gaps happened across various lower level project operations, and it have leads to false information dissemination and incomplete messages for stakeholders. In support with these insights key informants argued that stakeholders engagement were formally integrated into project implementation and plans. They have disclosed that feedback mechanism at the grass root level where poor that would reduce responsiveness and accountability.

Secondly regarding discussion on the project stakeholders engagement and communication. The study have found very good to excellent performance evaluation results and assured the strong practices in aspects of the stakeholders engagements, and communications. This finding demonstrated strong agreement on that the project stakeholders were familiarized and sensitized about the project objectives, deliverable, and expected outputs clearly and confusions were minimized. This finding is highly complement with the study conducted on urban social safety net project in Addis Ababa, which have found that clear and transparent communication significantly enhance beneficiary trust and program legitimacy in urban productive safety net project implementation practices (Berhane et al., 2019). The finding of this study have found that stakeholders communication were strong in urban productive social safety net implementation practices. On contrary, the study by Hoddinott et al., (2012) have found the rural productive social safety net project implementation have poor communication expressed in terms of weak feedback mechanism, and by limited community participation.

4. Conclusion

The study has investigated an evaluation of urban productive social safety net project implementation practices in cases of Nifas Silik Lafto Sub-city Addis Ababa, Ethiopia with the aim of understanding the project management practices. The findings on evaluation of project governance, and planning found strong compliance to integration, costs and project scope established frameworks management practices. While the study identified notable strengths in budget planning, proper resources allocation and strong financial control mechanisms the practices were consistent with government and donor financial management practices, certain gaps observed in coordination's and schedule management which have moderate variability across project implementer site (woreda) which have minimal effect on overall project accomplishments practices. These results highlights the importance of evaluation of project governance, and planning in enhancing the project integration, costs and scope management practices, and provided empirical evidences that can inform policy, practices and future program improvement areas. Though

limitation related to specific contextualized area and project specific concern, the study offers valuable insights and services as sources for future research works in the area of urban social safety net project implementation practices.

The finding of the study revealed that project implementations, and technical performance management practices were strongly performed on the areas such as quality, human resources and on procurement management practices. Overall, the result has indicated that project services packages such as public works, direct cash transfers, livelihood support services have meet the required project quality standards with the key strengths observed on routine supervision and technical backstopping. Furthermore, the finding in this theme has indicated that the project human resources management practices were very strong, with sufficient staffing and regular capacity building initiatives. However, moderate inconsistency in workload distributions, training access, and staff deployments were found. On the other indicator evaluation of procurement practices have exceptional strong performance finding on practices of project operation and have an excellent result on schedule management and transparency but, utilization of procured resources appropriateness were slightly varied across project implementer woredas (sites). Overall the findings on project implementation and technical performances on procurement procedures, human resources management and quality management were successful.

The study on evaluation of the project enabling environments creation was found strong in both the project risks management, and stakeholders' communication and engagement management practices. The finding has indicated that risk reduction; monitoring and mitigation strategies were institutionalized in the project activities but, moderate challenges such as payment delays and changes on the external social, political and economic conditions with the minimal impacts on project implementation progress. Similarly, the project stakeholder's communication and engagements management practices rated vary good to excellent performances with strong performances observed in effective participation of key stakeholders in planning, implementation, and evaluation project activities accomplishment progress with slight challenge on communication breakdowns and on uneven feedback communication mechanisms across project implementer woredas. These findings suggested that project key stakeholders communication and engagements management and risk management are critical for improving project activities accomplishments progress. Despite limitations related to slight inconsistency in the risks and stakeholders management practices across project implementer woredas, the study provided helpful

insights for project managers, social protection policy makers, practitioners and researchers.

In conclusion, this study has evaluated urban productive social safety net project implementation practices in case of Nifas Silik lafto Sub-city, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The evaluation finding indicated that project cost, scope, quality, human resources, procurement, risk management, and stakeholder engagement were effectively implemented lead to successful accomplishment project objectives. The additional strong finding founded that includes budget planning, resource allocation, financial controls, routine supervision, and technical backstopping that ensured project service packages met required quality standards which enhanced performances. Despite of it areas that needs improvement were observed in coordination, schedule management, workload distribution, training access, resource utilization, and communication consistency across implementing woredas due to operational and contextual factors. These variations had minimal impact on overall project accomplishments and their overall impacts on project outcomes remained insignificant.

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